

Advancing Orchestration: Leveraging Distance Functions to Meet Application Intents

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Abstract—True orchestration and management systems should manage applications based on their Service Level Objectives (SLOs), but this presents two key challenges: a) understanding how close an application’s current state is to its desired state, and b) defined by competing SLOs – and encapsulating user-defined priorities – where certain objectives may hold more weight, to enable effective arbitration. To address these challenges, we introduce a set of distance functions that measure the gap between an application’s current and desired states. These functions can guide planning and scheduling algorithms, refine utility and cost functions, and support arbitration between competing objectives. Implemented in Kubernetes-based systems, these distance functions enhance planning and scheduling efficiency, optimizing orchestration stacks to meet SLOs with greater precision and higher levels of efficiency.

Keywords—network orchestration, distance functions

I. INTRODUCTION

Orchestration and resource management encompass the life-cycle management of resources and applications, from incubation to retirement, with a focus on aligning the diverse priorities of application and infrastructure owners. Infrastructure owners focus on optimizing the total cost of ownership (TCO) and maximizing return on investment (ROI), while applications owners prioritize performance, cost-efficiency, and power consumption. An effective orchestration system must balance these objectives by managing service level objectives (SLOs) across the ecosystem, ensuring a holistic approach that meets all stakeholders’ goals.

Among the range of well-known tools that can be used for orchestration, Kubernetes¹ has gained significant popularity over recent years [1]. A challenge encountered in Kubernetes and other orchestration frameworks is that they are highly resource-oriented, where allocations are made based on specific resource requirements that need to be detailed *a priori*. This may cause sub-optimal performance or overpaying for resources [2]. In this context, Intent-Driven Orchestration (IDO) has emerged as a novel approach that proposes a paradigm shift from declarative resource requests to an intent-driven [3] way, where application owners can specify the goals or performance targets that applications should meet, rather than providing explicit resource quantities and configurations. By automating the process of configuring resources to meet the specified intents, IDO reduces the burden on application

owners, who no longer need to understand detailed system specifications but can focus on the desired outcomes for their applications.

An intent is a declaration made by an application owner that outlines the desired outcomes (declared objectives) for their application, such as latency, throughput, power, or availability targets, measured through Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) – sometimes referred to as Service Level Indicators (SLIs). For example, an application owner might specify an intent to maintain latency below 50 milliseconds while ensuring 99.9% availability. Each of these objectives corresponds to specific KPIs that provide measurable data points to track how well the application is meeting its intent.

A key component of enabling IDO is a planning component that automates orchestration actions - e.g., embedded in a Kubernetes control plane². This module continuously compares the current state of an application instance with the desired state, determining the necessary actions to align the two. For example, in a web application, the state might be defined by compute tail-latency metrics such as the P-50, P-95, and P-99 quantiles. Measuring the distance between current and desired states is crucial for the planning module to make informed and efficient decisions. Once these distances can be measured, they can serve multiple purposes:

- 1) **Heuristics** - Guiding problem-solving algorithms, such as scheduling and planning, to converge more efficiently on the desired state.
- 2) **Utility functions** - Quantifying the utility of an orchestration action in minimizing the gap between the current and desired application states.

Although distance functions can be applied in various contexts, such as solving algorithms, this paper focuses on their role in planning activities. Our main contribution consists of introducing a set of distance functions that, besides measuring the gap between the current and desired states of an application instance, are able to capture the priorities for different intents. The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II introduces various distance functions and their unique characteristics. Section III discusses how these characteristics can guide decision-making processes. Section IV evaluates the impact and performance of these approaches. Finally, Sections V and VI present related work and conclusions, respectively.

¹<https://kubernetes.io/>

²<https://github.com/intel/intent-driven-orchestration>

II. DISTANCE FUNCTIONS

Effective orchestration relies on measuring the gap between an application's current state and its desired state, as defined by Service Level Objectives (SLOs). To address this need, we introduce a set of distance functions that provide a quantitative basis for guiding orchestration decisions based on the SLOs.

A. Euclidean distance ($L2$)

The simplest function is the calculation of the Euclidean distance between two states. Let a desired state at time t with a set of $O(t) = \{o_1, o_2, \dots, o_n\}$ objectives, and $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ the measurable KPIs (such as latency, throughput, etc.). The current state is denoted as $S(t) = \{s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n\}$, where each value s_i denotes the corresponding value of the KPI measured at time t . For a given configuration s_i , the distance between s_i and o_i is computed as

$$D_p = \left[\sum_{i=1}^n (s_i - o_i)^p \right]^{1/p}. \quad (1)$$

When $p = 1$ this corresponds to the Manhattan (or $L1$) distance, while $p = 2$ is the baseline and currently implemented Euclidean distance (also referred as $L2$). The distance acts as a response on how far a state is from reaching the goal o_i . While the $L2$ distance is more precise as it is more sensitive to small differences, the $L1$ is computationally less expensive for high-dimensional spaces. As in more realistic scenarios the graph sizes are in the regime of low-dimensional spaces, we fix $L2$ as our baseline.

A limitation of this distance is that no importance of one objective over another is taken into account. For instance, given two states s_0 and s_1 with high and low priorities for the objectives, say o_{high} and o_{low} respectively, we might see a large distance if the difference for o_{low} for the states is large, while the difference between o_{high} for the objectives might be small. To cover such scenarios, we introduce an alternative distance function in the following subsection.

B. Importance distance (D_{Δ_I})

To support a notion of prioritization between competing objectives, a tolerance can be defined as a value that establishes how much of that objective can be changed (e.g. in form of percentage), representing how strict a certain declared intent is. In principle, the higher the tolerance, the less important an objective is, as there is more flexibility with changing the values for such objective. Therefore a distance function can be defined by adding weights to the individual objectives as

$$D_{\Delta_I} = \sqrt{\left(\sum_{i=1}^n w_i * |s_i - o_i|^2 \right)}, \quad (2)$$

such that lower weights are set for objectives with higher tolerance. The importance should have the form of $w_i = 1/(1 + \Delta_i)$, where the toleration for a given objective o_i as Δ_i stretches an objective to the maximum value it can take - a relaxing condition to the original target. This value

TABLE I: Measuring the distances

Distance	$D(s_1, s_2)$
Euclidean	24.49
Importance	16.07
Bounded	8.53

has the same dimensions as o_i , which is then inserted in the heuristics as a weight. The higher those values, the more the heuristics will be accounted for, thus prioritizing the objectives with higher importance. In comparison with the Euclidean, the weighting mechanism of the importance distance captures well the priorities of each intent, but adds an extra complexity to the problem due to its linear scaling. It also does not distinguish between the different natures of each KPI.

C. Bounded distance (D_{Δ_b})

Depending on the objective types, the goal should be bringing the current state to lower or higher values from its current ones. For instance, while typically the latency targets should be minimized to ensure a more responsive user experience, the throughput should often be maximized, as high throughput indicates is an indicator of effectiveness. The previously proposed distances do not capture this type of information. We thus introduce the *bounded distance* to account for both tolerations and objective types, defined as follows. If $o_i - \Delta_i \leq s_i \leq o_i + \Delta_i$, the current state has already reached the given target within bounds and no further action should be taken, setting $\delta = 0$ in

$$D_{\Delta_b} = \sum_{i=1}^n \sqrt{\delta_i * |o_i - s_i|^2}, \quad (3)$$

or $\delta = 1$ in the opposite scenario. This implies that if a state has not yet reached the values with the bounds, only the difference for that objective will be accounted for the overall distance between the two states. The primary goal is to define which objective is more important to be reached, based on the value of the bounds. In Table I we compare the different values for two given nodes of a state graph, with respective objectives defined as $s_1 = (P50 = 30, P95 = 90, P99 = 110)$ and $s_2 = (P50 = 20, P95 = 110, P99 = 120)$, with tolerations defined as $\Delta_i = (3.0, 1.0, 2.0)$. This means that P95 is more important than P99.

III. APPLYING DISTANCE FUNCTION TO ORCHESTRATION AND MANAGEMENT

For any decision making entity in the control plane (such as scheduling and planning algorithms), the distance functions are a key input as they determine how close the current state of an application is to the desired one. This is especially true in a context where a system should strive to satisfy the SLOs of the stakeholders. Algorithms can use these distance functions to rank and weight their options and hence pick the one that leads to the most efficient outcome.

Especially for use-cases where the goal is to enable application owners to define preferences among their targeted

objectives in their intents this is key. Such use-cases can include those where an application owner defines "a P99 latency target is more important to reach than a P50 latency target". Or cases where competing objectives are defined such as "it is more important to hit my power target than my performance target" (or vice-versa). Currently, neither of these use-cases would be possible in a pure resource requirement declarative way of defining an application manifest, and open up possibilities to a resource provider, as they now get more flexibility in how to run the applications given the additional context. These arbitration modes are only possible with the latter distance functions defined in section II.

The planning component determines a set of actions to get the current state of an application as close as possible to the desired state. Therefore, the planner constructs a state graph where nodes define the potential states, and the edges between them are sets of potential actions that can be taken, each with associated utility or cost. These utilities can be defined based on the preference of the resource provider, e.g. encapsulating the actual resources usage/cost associated with action. The set of most efficient actions are achieved by using a shortest-path search between current and desired states via the A* algorithm [4], a well-known path-finding method that finds the shortest path from the current to the desired state. An example is shown in Figure 1, where we show how a set of different actions can bring the source node to the target while minimizing the utility costs. The available actions can be, for instance, scaling in-out or up-down the number of resources, tuning resource allocations or platform settings, as well as removing POD instances.

Fig. 1: Illustration of a state graph with action costs annotated on the edges showing that an application with 273.125ms P95 tail latency can be scaled in to reach the target of 300ms.

The distance functions above defined play a key role for the planner in two ways: as heuristics to guide the algorithm itself, or as the basis for defining a utility/cost for performing an action, as detailed in the following subsections.

TABLE II: Measuring number of visited nodes.

Graph size	9	17	72	112
Importance	5	6	2	7
Euclidean	5	6	2	7
Bounded	4	6	2	7
No heuristic	3	4	12	6

A. Heuristic Guidance for Efficient Planning

In the context of A* search, heuristics play a critical role in guiding the algorithm toward faster convergence by reducing the number of node expansions required to reach the goal. Similarly, when enabling IDO, the planning algorithm benefits from prioritizing states that are closer to the application's desired state. This prioritization is especially crucial for larger state graphs, where effective heuristic implementation can significantly reduce the number of nodes that need to be explored, leading to more efficient planning.

The size and complexity of a state graph depend on several factors. If a single action can bring the current state closer to the desired one, the graph remains small. However, when multiple actions are needed, the graph expands in both breadth and depth. This complexity affects how well a heuristic can guide the planning. We have applied the distance functions as heuristics within the planner to evaluate their impact, as shown in Table II. The results indicate that for smaller state graphs, the benefit of using these heuristics is negligible, with performance similar to scenarios without heuristics. However, for larger and more complex state graphs, the heuristics help reduce the number of nodes explored by the A* algorithm. This demonstrates the practical advantage of integrating distance functions as heuristics, particularly in environments where the state graph grows in complexity. The distance functions include notions of the objectives that need to be fulfilled, explaining their effectiveness. While the current planning algorithm and state graph construction showcase these benefits, further optimizations and alternative algorithms may unlock even greater efficiency gains.

B. Utility Functions for Decision-Making

Beyond utilizing distance functions as heuristics, they can also serve as a basis for defining the utility or cost of executing actions. This is particularly relevant when arbitration is required between competing objectives within the intents defined for an application. In our current planner, actions associated with lower-cost edges are considered more favorable. Consequently, a higher utility for an action is represented by a lower numerical cost on the edge, where the closer to zero the more desirable an edge is - and subsequently overall path in the state graph.

The cost of transitioning between states is governed by utility functions that are adjustable by the resource provider, which can be based on the costs of resources required, priority of the application, available capacity among others. This approach enables the planner to prioritize one path over another. In scenarios where not all objectives can be met simultaneously, distance functions can enable an arbitration model by

calculating the costs for edges that connect intermediate states to the desired goal. In such cases, the planner can determine which set of actions most effectively advances the current state of the application towards the desired state, even if not all objectives can be reached. The arbitration model hence incorporates the concept of importance among objectives, as captured by the distance functions accounting for both bounds and priorities, as discussed in Section II.

To translate distances into costs, a normalization is required, as the distances include application-specific objectives that can have various value ranges. In this context, the Softmax normalization method is a suitable candidate, converting the non-normalized distances into a probability distribution, with the temperature parameter T acting as a factor that controls the influence of the distance on the overall plan of actions, defined as $\text{softmax}(x_i) = \frac{e^{\frac{x_i}{T}}}{\sum_{j=1}^N e^{\frac{x_j}{T}}}$, with x_i the non-normalized distances. By introducing T , an additional tuning knob is made available to the resource provider. As illustrated in Figure 2, the temperature acts as an activation term that influences how distances are accounted for. A higher temperature smooths the distribution, leading to a more even distribution of the cost, while lower temperatures accentuates differences, making the largest distances more influential. In other words, when the temperature increases, the normalized values begin to converge, which reduces the impact of distances — and, consequently, the prioritization specified by the application owner through tolerances. In such cases, the cost calculated based on the tunable utility functions becomes more dominant, allowing the resource provider greater control over which action the planner will select. A lower temperature results in values being normalized between 0 and 1, with the state closest to the desired state being favored. This, in turn, enhances the arbitration process by ensuring that the planner prioritizes actions that align more closely with the application owner’s intended objectives.

Fig. 2: Effects of the temperature in the softmax normalization when applied to four distances [3.464, -0.404, 3.162, 1.732].

The effects of arbitration and temperature control are shown in Figure 3. In the first scenario Figure 3a, a more costly action (*Action A*) is selected because it brings the system closer to the

desired state as defined by the application owner’s intent. In contrast, the second scenario in Figure 3b demonstrates a case where a less expensive action is chosen due to the influence of tolerances on the distance calculation, potentially resulting in cost savings for the application owner and resource saving benefits for the resource provider. Lastly, Figure 3c shows that by increasing the temperature, the resource provider effectively deactivates the distance function preferences, leading to the selection of the less costly *Action B*.

IV. EVALUATION OF THE DISTANCE FUNCTIONS

To evaluate the proposed distance functions, we measure their overall performance in terms of execution time (how efficient it is to compute them). As the distance functions are primarily used as heuristics for the planning algorithm, we measure the impact of the distance in the context of their usage as heuristics. We compared their impact on the total planning time by measuring their performance across the different dimensions, using Go’s *pprof* profiling tool³, which allow us to collect detailed system performance data, such as CPU usage and memory allocations. We focus on the CPU cycles spent on planning, which is crucial for understanding how computing the different distance functions can affect the overall planning efficiency. To test the scalability of these metrics, we generated synthetic state graphs by changing the number of nodes and objectives. When changing the number of nodes, we fixed 4 objectives in each node with defined values for P-99, P-95 and P-50 latency, as well as for the throughput. On the other hand, when changing the number of objectives, we fix a state graph with 80 nodes, allowing to isolate the impact that the number of objectives have on the performance of the distance functions. As for the tolerations, we randomly selected a range of values between [0.1-15], defining the priorities for each objective. These values were selected based on examples that are often considered from scenarios we tested, both for graph sizes and number of objectives. We then ran a series of 1000 iterations for each distance to gather performance data. We expect that this will point towards finding which functions are most effective under the different conditions.

We have categorized the different state graph sizes into small, medium and large, with most of our test system sizes falling into the small category. The size intervals were respectively set as [0-180], [180-360], and [360-500] nodes.

Regardless of the chosen distance function, the planning time increases only slightly as the graph size grows, with similar overall performance across functions. While the euclidean distance performs well for medium-sized graphs as shown in Figure 4, with an average of 21.47% of the overall planning time, it does worse than the other distances for the larger graphs. Instead, the importance distance has the worse performance for small graphs, with an average of 32.65%, but does better than the euclidean for the larger ones, with an average of 25.22%. Last, the bounded distance has the best performance for smaller graphs, with an average of 21.70%,

³<https://go.dev/blog/pprof>

Fig. 3: Distance functions influence the planning algorithm’s decision-making process when calculating the costs of different actions. The planner aims to reach a goal state defined by three latency objectives: P50 at 25ms, P95 at 50ms, and P99 at 60ms. Both Actions A and B move the application closer to the desired state, but the P50 target remains unachievable. The choice between actions depends on the set tolerances and configured temperature, leading to recommend different actions.

and 24.82% for larger graphs. As the graph size increases, the complexity of the planning problem also grows, and the set of paths between current and target states through the graph becomes bigger. In this scenario, the ability to prioritize certain paths gives the importance distance an advantage, as it can reduce the number of paths that need to be explored on the state graph. These small variations show that distance functions enhance planning capabilities without significantly impacting computation time, making them a valuable tool for efficient path planning.

While the bounded distance may not always outperform the Euclidean one, it remains a viable alternative that can offer comparable or improved performance depending on the scenario. Calculating more complex distances on smaller graphs can increase overall planning time, but as the graph size increases, the benefits of prioritizing certain objectives become more evident, leading to more efficient planning.

Fig. 4: Measuring performance based on the overall consumption of the distances with respect to the planning time.

In Figure 5, we notice that the distance contributes more to the overall planning time as the number of objectives increases.

For a range of $O = [0 - 30]$, the importance distance shows a similar performance, as it contributes with an average of 3.0%, while Euclidean has 3.16% and Bounded 3.5%. In this scenario, computing these functions is relatively simple, and the differences in performance between them are marginal. As the number of objectives increases, the Euclidean distance shows better performance than Bounded and Importance, with an average of 7.3% for states with $O = [30 - 60]$. This happens because either computing the importance for each additional objective, or adding comparative statements for checking if a certain objective is within the bounds, introduces complexity for the new computations, a step that is not required for the Euclidean distance.

Fig. 5: Measuring performance based on the different number of objectives.

In summary, there is no single best distance measure in terms of execution time; each has its own advantages and trade-offs, which are problem-dependent, as shown in Figure 5 and Figure 4. Depending on the application owner’s goals, selecting the importance distance incorporates additional problem-specific information for different objectives.

This can be more computationally intensive but potentially more effective for larger graphs where such information is crucial for efficient planning. The evaluations show that the importance and bounded distance functions offer functionalities that the Euclidean distance does not, such as enabling an arbitration model that prioritizes objectives. We conclude that using advanced distance functions for planning and scheduling can be beneficial, as this is a key feature of what true orchestration systems should be capable of.

V. RELATED WORK

In the context of managing application SLOs, previous work has predominantly focused on managing SLAs [5]–[7]. SLAs are often viewed as binary contractual agreements: either fulfilled or not. While negotiation schemes between application owners and resource providers have been explored, these models remain rigid. By introducing distance functions to enable arbitration modes, this paper adopts a more intent-driven model, allowing application owners to define tolerations and express preferences. This enables resource providers, such as cloud and edge providers, to use this context information to make more informed decisions, as discussed in Section III.

Utility and cost functions have been extensively used in prior work [8]–[10], often guiding scheduling algorithms or optimization processes. These cost functions typically reflect stakeholder preferences, such as balancing available versus requested resources, but do not always incorporate the nuanced requirements of application owners, especially when prioritized SLOs need to be met.

The distance functions introduced in this paper can be applied to a wider range of problems. While similar functions have been used in optimization algorithms (e.g., as fitness functions) [11], [12], using distance functions for arbitration is novel and demonstrates the advantages of an IDO model. This model enhances semantic application portability, provides contextual awareness, and empowers resource providers to configure systems that meet stakeholders’ objectives, rather than merely delivering fixed quantities of requested resources that may go underutilized.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we introduced a set of distance functions designed to capture the gap between an application’s current state, as defined by its SLOs, and its desired state. These distance functions are particularly useful in guiding decision-making in two significant ways: as heuristics to guide problem-solving and scheduling algorithms, and as the utility costs associated with decisions affecting the application or system state. By incorporating tolerances into the distance functions, which allow for the prioritization of one or more objectives, we enable a robust arbitration model. This model provides resource providers the ability to determine what is most important to the application owner and make informed decisions accordingly. This ability to prioritize is especially crucial in an IDO model, where stakeholders define what they want to achieve rather than how to achieve it. In this framework,

resource providers gain more flexibility to optimize platform and infrastructure efficiency. For application owners, this model offers enhanced application portability, allowing their applications to be effectively managed across different environments. Additionally, the context defined by stakeholders guides decision-making, enabling future orchestration systems to trade off between objectives, such as prioritizing power efficiency over performance. Future work will explore the definition of additional distance functions and further evaluate their application in advanced planning and scheduling techniques.

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